

1 **Target discovery in Panic Disorder.**

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6 Psychiatric illnesses have historically been thought to lack an obvious physiologic component, plainly
7 evident in humans with Panic Disorder (PD). We used peripheral blood of patients with disease for drug
8 target discovery. We document here multiple defects in solute transport function in the peripheral blood in
9 humans with panic disorder. We observed activation of *SLC48A1* and *SLC6A12*. The sodium
10 voltage-gated channel alpha subunit *SCN9A* was a major target of repression. Patients with panic disorder
11 lacked expression of *CCL13* in the blood.

12 Citations

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